

Multi-dimensional cubic symmetric block cipher algorithm for encrypting big data

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ABSTRACT

The advanced technology in the internet and social media, communication companies, health care records and cloud computing applications made the data around us increase dramatically every minute and continuously. These renewals big data involve sensitive information such as password, PIN number, credential numbers, secret identifications and etc. which require maintaining with some high secret procedures. The present paper involves proposing a secret multi-dimensional symmetric cipher with six dimensions as a cubic algorithm. The proposed algorithm works with the substitution permutation network (SPN) structure and supports a high processing data rate in six directions. The introduced algorithm includes six symmetry rounds transformations for encryption the plaintext, where each dimension represents an independent algorithm for big data manipulation. The proposed cipher deals with parallel encryption structures of the 128-bit data block for each dimension in order to handle large volumes of data. The submitted cipher compensates for six algorithms working simultaneously each with 128-bit according to various irreducible polynomials of order eight. The round transformation includes four main encryption stages where each stage with a cubic form of six dimensions.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The cryptographic algorithms are a set of rules and mathematical procedures that are used to convert the clear text to an unintelligible text and vice-versa. There are basically two types of the first is cryptographic algorithms of public key cryptography (PKC) or what is called asymmetric cipher where the sender and receiver use two keys one for encryption and the other for the decryption process. The second is secret key cryptography (SKC) also known as symmetric encryption. The symmetric cipher plays an effective role for a trusted block of data where the sender and receiver own the same secret key [1]. The proposed cipher represents a smart step in the designing process of symmetric block cipher construction. The submitted algorithm is dedicated to big data applications and it inherited most of its good characteristics from previously published algorithms [2-4]. Big data refers to the large data sets that increased dramatically and grown continuously from different sources. So the data classified today as the traditional data tomorrow will be big data since the data is evolving without stopping due to the advanced technology of the web applications and the electronic business services [5]. The big data is unlike traditional data because it needs a high potential that outweighs the conventional data from all aspects. So it should take into consideration the designing of a large cipher to meet the growth of data and the cipher should be convenient for the big

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volume of data because it became a necessary demand. The big data is not considered new data due to a huge historical data amount created from the earlier time that belongs to deep roots and an extended origin of old data [6]. Big data become a critical issue in recent years as a result of increased the growth of the internet and electronic communications, cloud services and social networks. The amounts of multimedia data generated within social networks are increasing without stopping [7]. Big data has become everywhere and definitively for several application domains. In a big data scenario, the data itself can be mapped to four distinct prototypes: data at rest, data in motion, data in many forms, and data in doubt. Moreover; there exist three forms of data integration in any enterprise: bulk data movement, real-time, and federation [8].

The big data interests with better analysis of the large bulks of data which support more intelligent decision and apply big profitability represented by smart decision, fast decision and impactful decision. Big data has powerful potential for making faster analysis in many scientific disciplines and the success of many enterprises [9]. Since the big data deals with a volume of data is very big and it generates and increases dramatically. Thus it will require a high processing capability compared with the traditional data need. Big data represents an aggregation of data from different kinds that involve current traditional data and an old one, it also includes a mixture of different types of structured and unstructured or multi-structured data that come from various sources [10]. In terms of unstructured data which instantiated from the data set that is not ordered or easily represented by traditional data models. So, social media or what is known as social networks such as Facebook, Tweeter, YouTube and other media from the point of view posts, comments and publications are considered good examples for this type of data. The case of multi-structured data, it indicates diversities of data sorts and formats that can be generated from users and devices, such as current social networks and web services as well as user interactions. The structured data are good examples of big data that may include the combination of text and images in addition to transactional information [11].

There are several distinct block cipher algorithms available that work with different structures and various mathematical descriptions. The present study will focus on the most common symmetric ciphers especially the standard ciphers that involve: IDEA, Triple-DES, AES, Twofish, Serpent, MARS, and RC6. Xuejia Lai and James Massey submitted an International Data Encryption Algorithm (IDEA). It is a new variant of symmetric cipher that was planned to be a replacement for the DES cipher. IDEA cipher encrypts electronic data of 64-bit using a 128-bit ciphering key under the Lai-Massey structure with 8.5 rounds. The IDEA cipher has been analyzed and broken in 2011 via the man in the middle attack and in 2012 full round was cryptanalytic by bicliques attack [12]. IBM Corporation develops Triple DES. It is a revised version for the IBM oldest cipher of data encryption standard (DES) that encrypts the data with a short secret key of 56-bit and Feistel structure. The Triple-DES or 3DES is the three times implementation process for the DES cipher under the length of secret key 168-bit and 48-rounds, although the Triple-DES suffered from the slow implementation it still applying in several civil applications and electronic financial services [13].

National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) released the Rijndael cipher as an advance encryption standard (AES) cipher. AES is the name for the block cipher that selected by NIST under the Rijndael name that designed by Vincent Rijmen and Joan Daemen in 1998. The Rijndael block cipher works with SPN structure and encrypts a block of data with a fixed length of 128-bit under three changeable ciphering keys according to the NIST criteria. The AES cipher is inspired by square cipher and is considered the best ciphering model, which is the most widely used algorithm for large scale applications presently [14]. Bruce Schneier et al., designed a Twofish cipher, Twofish is a revision block cipher algorithm for the previous blowfish block cipher. Twofish encrypts a block size of 128 bits and three of different ciphering key reaches 256 bits. It was a finalist candidate to be advanced encryption standard and as an alternated for the 3DES. Twofish algorithm works with 16-rounds of iterated Feistel structure of key-dependent S-Boxes [15]. Ross Anderson et al., designed a Serpent block cipher that is one of the best five finalist symmetric algorithms with SPN structure. Serpent algorithm encrypts the electronic data with a block size of 128-bits and also three different ciphering keys like the AES cipher. The serpent cipher can be implemented in a parallel structure of 32-rounds according to 32-bit of the bit-slices technique [16].

MARS cipher submitted by IBM Corporation, acts a revised cipher for the DES cipher and encrypts the electronic data with block size and key size similar to any AES candidate cipher. MARS encrypts the data via a variable secret key that ranging from 128-bit to 444-bit. MARS characterized by complex structure since it depends on heavy mathematical operations. Thus; it considers the most complicated cipher among the candidates' algorithms [17]. Rivest *et al.* [18] designed an RC6 algorithm that considers the simplest and easiest model as the AES candidate algorithm. RC6 cipher represents a revision form of the previous RC5 cipher but with double size. RC6 encrypts the electronic data with block length and a key length of 128-bit and the secret ciphering key can be up to 2040-bit. RC6 designed with Feistel network structure of four words each with 32-bit, which is iterated for 20-rounds completely [18].

In response to the security challenge, the proposed cipher is designed to face real attacks and to solve the traditional security problems in this field. The protection of private and confidential data attracted the researchers' attention for a long time. So, the basic challenge for the security of big data is data privacy.

The trusted multimedia issues have become critical and necessary in social network and cloud environments because the malicious attacks are becoming more sophisticated and new active malwares have been developed recently [19]. The vulnerability of security systems or fault of security designs can lead to big losses that may exceed even the worst expectations and introduce irreplaceable damage for a company or organization. Since, sensitive data has become accessible from anywhere and the potential of risks for malicious use is made possible. The questions beyond the ethical usage of data and data privacy become momentous. Since big data platforms introduce a broad array of likelihoods to access internal and external data. Unfortunately, most organizations that deal with big data face the same issues of daily threats [20]. Nowadays, most agencies look forward to ensuring that their information are kept securely. So the protect data with all these trends require an appropriate cipher that satisfies the real issues. The developed cipher must defeat the current challenges of end to end encryption, protected user access control, password management and safeguarding internal and external secret information at all levels. Big data terminology needs special cryptographic algorithms with an extended structure of large size or that one with the multi-dimensional cipher of parallel encryption process [21, 22]. The security in such milieu comprises more data stored, which means more security procedures and more modern policies of secrecy that should be taken into consideration to apply the privacy in an effective form. So, “a big question is to what extent the security and privacy technology are adequate for controlled assured sharing for efficient direct access to big data?” [23].

2. RESEARCH METHOD

The proposed cubic cipher works with 16-bytes as a state matrix of 128-bit for each independent face or dimension in the cubic algorithm. Moreover; the cubic algorithm can work with six dimensions together in a parallel form that meaning the data blocks are 6×128 -bit. The proposed cipher accepts 128-bits of plaintext from each side in the cube and 128-bits of ciphering secret key as the initial of entry secret key XORed at the first and last rounds according to the whitening concepts. The main operations in the round transformation involve cubic operations with six options according to the cube dimensions. The internal stages for each algorithm aggregated in the round transformation encompass four fundamental stages looped for some rounds. The implementation cubic algorithm as an individual algorithm is subject to the modular arithmetic process. The selected dimension in the cubic algorithm is determined by the least significant byte (LSB) in the ciphering key mod 7 for each round. The result will be less than 7, which represents the dimension number in the cube with range (1-6). Dimension Number (DN)=LSB mod 7. The round transformation of the proposed cipher comprises the following four main stages as stated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The cubic algorithm structure

2.1. Non-linear black-box stages

This stage is considered the most important part of designing any algorithm which determines the solidity and strength of the algorithm. The proposed black-box consists of six faces or dimensions, whereby each dimension works with the different irreducible polynomial equation as stated in Figures 2-7. The collected dimensions constitute a cube of active black-boxes and each cube face or dimension can be represented as a table lookup of 16*16 values. The intersection of the i^{th} row and j^{th} column in the table for each face gives the desired value. Each Black-box design is constructed similar to the S-Box of AES cipher in terms of taking the multiplicative inverse and applying the affine transform XORed with certain constant vectors of (V1, V2 ... V6) as shown in the equations below:

$$\text{Black-S1}[x] = \text{Affine}(x^{-1}) + V1 \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Black-S2}[x] = \text{Affine}(x^{-1}) + V2 \tag{2}$$

$$\text{Black-S3}[x] = \text{Affine}(x^{-1}) + V3 \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Black-S4}[x] = \text{Affine}(x^{-1}) + V4 \tag{4}$$

$$\text{Black-S5}[x] = \text{Affine}(x^{-1}) + V5 \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Black-S6}[x] = \text{Affine}(x^{-1}) + V6 \tag{6}$$

	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
00	AD	4B	1C	8C	75	4D	3D	6C	19	4D	DD	46	E5	F5	CA	8E
01	59	CF	F3	97	95	00	58	E6	89	3A	43	BA	DC	F4	FE	62
02	15	E8	9C	87	82	2D	72	9A	B1	3B	B9	A3	57	A0	08	C9
03	7D	D4	66	0F	18	44	E4	EF	D7	6B	01	13	C6	38	88	4A
04	33	F0	CD	0A	F7	59	B8	21	F8	C8	2F	10	42	C7	36	A3
05	61	BC	24	05	65	B0	68	CC	D0	93	E9	D2	BD	81	5D	76
06	C5	1E	D3	ED	8A	37	3E	54	77	C9	B9	F9	CB	EA	4E	AE
07	52	0D	CE	31	FB	85	F2	D5	DA	FF	A5	DF	3F	2B	5E	A4
08	20	55	03	E7	5F	6D	7E	AC	80	34	B7	E0	27	7C	29	C3
09	07	83	1F	32	EC	D9	73	BE	5A	7A	98	6E	60	6A	6C	B5
0A	09	49	25	BF	69	11	78	D8	0B	05	23	2E	4F	A8	1D	DB
0B	D1	53	70	9F	8F	7F	12	6F	D7	67	79	A1	17	E2	40	B4
0C	5B	30	B6	1A	50	4C	8D	23	FC	AA	22	41	64	0C	51	C2
0D	02	AFA	79D	7492	45	8B	9E	B2	0E	71	5C	39	2C	2A		
0E	90	1B	FD	BB	DE	B3	E3	35	86	FA	7B	C4	C0	04	91	19
0F	16	14	84	A2	A9	48	56	E1	26	F1	EE	F6	96	47	EB	A6

Figure 2. Forward black-box1

	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
00	AD	4B	E6	20	08	D6	6B	1A	47	3F	10	9F	CE	B3	4E	84
01	E0	65	DC	D2	73	6A	8C	38	24	27	A2	F3	5C	6C	39	15
02	33	C5	F1	D4	2D	96	12	C2	FAB	4	76	04	3D	48	57	79
03	69	5D	E8	3A	2A	A8	82	E4	55	01	4D	A3	E7	28	C9	C0
04	DA	59	A1	7C	BB	1F	29	FD	5	97	30	36	4A	87	22	1E
05	3E	B6	21	FD	40	0F	41	EC	E5	45	67	9E	D0	EE	C7	51
06	F7	9D	ED	A5	37	AA	66	81	56	77	17	5A	02	49	31	94
07	E9	E1	FB	FC	DD	AE	92	DE	B0	19	6F	8A	A7	CA	1B	B7
08	16	74	EF	8E	AB	03	7D	5F	A6	07	F4	C1	D7	4F	3C	F2
09	91	FF	88	B9	5B	B2	60	C6	5E	AC	B8	61	52	46	4C	53
0A	64	AF	18	42	D3	85	BD	C0	63	99	C4	93	DB	3B	55	7F
0B	89	BA	D9	9A	C8	7B	34	0E	2B	54	0C	98	2F	EB	0D	
0C	80	78	B5	D1	8D	1D	A9	72	D5	9C	2E	11	70	EA	83	C3
0D	68	13	F8	75	F0	38	6E	9B	7A	50	DF	44	E3	0B	09	F5
0E	8F	F9	8B	E2	86	00	05	43	95	BE	2C	0A	32	BC	14	BF
0F	23	71	CF	A4	CC	62	06	25	90	6D	26	7E	F6	B1	A0	1C

Figure 3. Forward black-box2

	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
00	AD	4B	CD	ED	8E	70	8D	99	2F	A3	50	07	AE	06	B7	19
01	ECC	1B	9E	25	53	AB	EB	29	2C	7A	78	4A	A0	34	E4	87
02	1E	56	88	8C	B4	5D	0A	25	D2	6F	BD	1F	9D	F0	FC	55
03	6D	5B	46	89	54	8A	5E	98	38	2E	72	80	1A	F6	B8	AF
04	67	4E	43	8F	3F	A5	3D	79	21	59	C6	31	7E	49	FA	F3
05	12	CA	CC	FF	B6	B1	F4	9C	B5	BE	03	94	05	00	C2	4F
06	DE	CE	D6	E6	58	4D	AC	39	51	2A	2D	D8	47	D1	24	FD
07	74	18	7F	FB	42	9F	3B	7B	65	76	13	F1	27	C3	BF	23
08	C8	28	5C	17	C9	7C	BC	6A	F7	AA	A9	1B	E5	66	C7	C5
09	F8	97	CA	DC	0B	60	E3	30	44	02	DF	9E	15	75	82	A1
0A	61	A2	0D	73	1D	6B	84	6C	33	3C	B0	71	01	E0	26	EF
0B	B2	62	37	64	E9	4C	22	9B	F9	8B	68	D0	09	63	CF	95
0C	14	A5	0F	11	10	B3	08	20	57	E1	DD	16	3E	32	E7	F3
0D	C0	85	7D	3A	FE	A6	04	0E	CB	D4	93	1C	69	D9	96	36
0E	52	0C	77	83	D7	EE	86	2B	5A	6E	A7	41	F5	BA	D5	D3
0F	DA	35	40	92	F2	81	90	91	E8	5F	9A	45	A4	DB	EA	BB

Figure 4. Forward black-box3

	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
00	AD	4B	85	9D	E2	42	B5	6B	0A	10	5A	5E	FA	49	CE	65
01	7E	87	73	E9	0D	4E	0F	0E	5D	9B	DF	39	47	03	92	71
02	44	74	B8	57	99	3A	8F	A5	FD	B0	5C	40	A7	4C	7C	EC
03	8E	9F	ED	26	CF	91	E7	1C	83	CC	A1	89	32	E1	C3	61
04	02	16	1A	31	27	43	D0	04	B7	37	66	E0	BC	B1	A9	54
05	DE	FF	23	D1	55	D4	00	B6	F3	3D	06	EE	1E	AC	56	46
06	67	C2	EF	88	8D	FB	33	F7	9C	38	B3	07	D3	6C	75	B2
07	BA	6D	1D	53	AB	15	E4	F2	62	29	8B	A6	9A	F6	90	70
08	7A	19	2B	8C	2D	5FE	09	E8	95	81	2E	48	C6	22	DA	
09	A0	1B	BB	12	13	6A	50	2C	25	98	F8	30	AF	01	51	C5
0A	14	F0	84	77	EA	DC	93	4F	8A	64	4A	D6	20	72	7B	60
0B	82	35	E5	6F	78	D5	0C	7F	2F	D8	76	21	0B	34	58	A8
0C	C8	24	41	3B	D7	D9	3F	CE	E6	CA	86	63	B9	45	80	08
0D	6E	05	3C	BF	A2	97	A3	CB	C9	BD	4D	DB	C1	69	79	1F
0E	7D	F4	96	C7	AE	94	D2	C0	F5	CD	AA	DD	52	FE	59	C4
0F	11	9E	B4	F1	BE	EB	28	2A	36	A4	5B	3E	68	F9	18	17

Figure 5. Forward black-box4

	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
00	AD	4B	54	FC	51	6E	05	3D	59	DD	C6	EA	F9	1B	E5	EC
01	5D	6D	95	D5	92	94	0E	33	0D	34	F6	8E	89	6F	87	17
02	5F	37	47	F5	B1	20	91	E0	32	F2	BB	25	7C	BF	68	39
03	FD	01	EB	12	8A	7A	B6	15	35	2B	CC	0A	B8	DA	F0	BA
04	D4	A0	6A	99	52	19	0B	80	29	AB	6B	DC	B3	3C	81	90
05	62	6C	88	36	A6	CB	63	AE	CF	C5	A4	ED	4F	9D	E7	1F
06	0F	3E	FB	DB	04	96	F8	18	B4	69	46	14	AA	43	7B	D6
07	E1	2D	EE	3A	1D	E3	7E	5C	27	06	16	98	03	2A	AC	09
08	9B	C2	A1	5A	C4	F7	B0	D8	C8	7D	38	74	BE	3B	9A	
09	65	5B	24	DE	CE	D3	9F	41	A2	F1	EF	C7	31	4E	B9	97
0A	C0	2F	4D	23	3F	8C	60	1A	28	CD	9E	FE	CA	85	2C	48
0B	9C	84	13	BC	A3	22	8D	08	56	83	B5	E2	02	C9	F4	D2
0C	76	75	64	A5	86	B2	1C	A8	F3	49	30	A9	07	40	77	C1
0D	21	4A	45	11	38	72	71	D1	2E	9F	50	AF	4C	82	10	DF
0E	8B	C3	67	93	0C	57	66	42	7F	D9	00	79	44	61	55	5E
0F	E8	73	78	1E	FA	D7	BD	70	53	E4	26	A7	E6	FF	8F	

Figure 6. Forward black-box5

	00	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	0A	0B	0C	0D	0E	0F
00	AD	4B	A1	A5	AB	00	A9	A8	D1	51	04	F2	AF	1E	50	63
01	93	BD	AC	C9	06	C1	7D	96	D3	A6	0B	F9	53	98	CA	9D
02	CD	42	DA	D9	52	77	E0	BE	78	66	E4	FE	C5	CB	30	FA
03	ED	DF	28	F7	81	24	F8	01	D2	11	48	5F	61	D8	B5	89
04	E2	B1	5A	3C	16	32	97	2B	2D	DD	BF	6C	74	56	5B	C3
05	38	EC	37	7C	76	64	7B	A2	E6	36	9E	A0	1C	10	79	7F
06	8D	6A	EB	5D	6F	7E	80	46	C4	09	69	F0	07	90	FB	4E
07	12	35	8C	C8	20	83	D4	8F	B4							

2.2. Inverse-non-linear black-box

The inverse Black box stage involves the construction of inverse-cube of six inv-black box lookup tables, where each with 256-bytes and with different irreducible polynomial as stated in Figures 8-13. When the encryption is done by the forward black-box1 the decryption should be by backward inv-black-box1 to ensure the compatibility operations, because the black-box tables are designed with different affine equations, different irreducible polynomials and various constant vectors.

	00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F
00	15 3A D0 82 ED A9 53 90 2E A0 43 A8 CD 71 DA 33
01	4B A5 B6 3B F1 20 F0 BC 34 EF C3 E1 02 AE 61 92
02	80 47 CA AA 52 A2 F8 8C C7 E8 DF 7D DE 25 AB 4A
03	C1 73 93 40 89 E7 4E 65 3D DD 19 29 69 06 66 7C
04	BE CB 4C 1A 35 D6 0B FD F5 A1 3F 01 C5 05 6E AC
05	C4 CE 70 B1 67 81 F6 2C 16 10 98 C0 DC 5E 7E 84
06	9C 50 1F 07 CC 54 32 B8 56 A4 9D 39 9E 85 9B B7
07	B2 DB 26 96 D4 04 5F 68 A6 BA 99 EA 8D 30 86 B5
08	88 5D 24 91 F2 75 E8 23 3E 18 64 D7 03 C6 0F B4
09	E0 EE D5 59 09 14 FC 13 9A 45 27 6A 22 D3 D8 B3
0A	2D BB F3 2B 7F 7A FF D2 AD F4 C9 4F 87 00 6F D1
0B	55 28 D9 E5 BF 9F C2 8A 46 2A 1B E3 51 5C 97 A3
0C	EC 08 CF 8F EB 60 3C 4D 49 2F 0E 6C 57 42 72 11
0D	58 B0 5B 62 31 77 B9 38 A7 95 78 AF 1C 0A E4 7B
0E	8B F7 BD E6 36 0C 17 83 21 5A 6D FE 94 63 FA 37
0F	41 F9 76 12 1D 0D FB 44 48 6B E9 74 C8 E2 1E 79

Figure 8. Backward black-box1

	00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F
00	E5 39 6C 85 2B E6 F6 89 04 DE EB DD BA BF B7 55
01	0A CB 26 D1 EE 1F 80 6A A2 79 07 7E FF C5 4F 45
02	03 52 4E F0 18 F7 FA 19 3D 46 34 B8 EA 24 CA BD
03	4A 6E EC 20 B6 AE 4B 64 D5 1E 33 AD 8E 2C 50 09
04	54 56 A3 E7 DB 59 D0 08 2D 6D 4C 01 9E 3A 0E 8D
05	D9 5F 9C 9F B9 38 68 2E 17 41 6B 94 1C 31 98 87
06	96 9B F5 A8 A0 11 66 5A D0 30 15 06 1D F9 D6 7A
07	CC F1 C7 14 81 D3 2A 69 C1 2F D8 B5 43 86 FB AF
08	C0 67 36 CE 0F A5 E4 4D 92 B0 7B E2 16 C4 83 E0
09	F8 90 76 AB 6F E8 25 49 BC A9 B3 D7 C9 61 5B 0B
0A	FE 42 1A 3B F3 63 88 7C 35 C6 65 84 99 00 75 A1
0B	78 FD 95 0D 29 C2 51 7F 9A 93 B1 44 ED A6 E9 EF
0C	3F 8B 27 CF AA 21 97 5E B4 3E 7D BB F4 A7 0C F2
0D	5C 33 13 A4 23 48 05 8C C8 B2 40 AC 12 74 77 DA
0E	10 71 E3 DC 37 58 02 3C 32 70 CD BE 57 62 5D 82
0F	D4 22 8F 1B 8A DF FC 60 D2 E1 28 72 73 53 47 91

Figure 9. Backward black-box2

	00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F
00	5D AC 99 5A D6 5C 0D 0B C6 BC 26 94 E1 A2 D7 C2
01	C4 C3 50 7A C0 9C CB 83 71 0F 3C 8B DB A4 20 2B
02	C7 48 B6 7F 6E 27 AE 7C 81 17 69 E7 18 6A 39 08
03	97 4B CD A8 1D F1 DF B2 38 67 D3 76 A9 46 CC 44
04	F2 EB 74 42 98 FB 32 6C CF 4D 1B 01 B5 65 41 5F
05	0A 68 E0 14 34 2F 21 C8 64 49 E8 31 82 25 36 F9
06	95 A0 B1 BD B3 78 8D 40 BA DC 87 A5 A7 30 E9 29
07	05 AB 3A A3 70 9D 79 E2 1A 47 19 77 85 D2 4C 72
08	3B F5 9E E3 A6 D1 E6 1F 22 33 55 B9 23 06 04 43
09	F6 F7 F3 DA 5B BF DE 91 37 07 FA B7 57 2C 9B 75
0A	1C 9F A1 09 FC 45 D5 EA C1 8A 89 15 66 00 0C 3F
0B	AA 55 B0 C5 24 58 54 0E 3E 12 ED FF 86 2A 59 7E
0C	D0 11 5E 7D 92 8F 4A 8E 80 84 51 D8 52 02 61 BE
0D	BB 6D 28 EF D9 EE 62 E4 6B DD F0 FD 93 CA 60 9A
0E	AD C9 13 96 1E 8C 63 CE F8 B4 FE 16 10 03 E5 AF
0F	2D 7B F4 4F 56 EC 3D 88 90 B8 4E 73 2E 6F D4 53

Figure 10. Backward black-box3

	00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F
00	56 9D 40 1D 47 D1 5A 6B CF 87 08 BCB6 14 17 16
01	09 F0 93 94 A0 75 41 FFFE 81 42 91 37 72 5CDF
02	AC BB 8E 52 C1 98 33 44 F6 79 F7 82 97 84 8B B8
03	9B 43 3C 66 BD B1 F8 49 69 1B 25 C3 D2 59 FB C6
04	2B C2 05 45 20 CD 5F 1C 8C 0D AA 01 2DDA 15 A7
05	96 9E C7 73 4F 54 5E 23 BE EE 0A FA 2A 18 0B 85
06	AF 3F 78 CB A9 0F 4A 60 FC DD 95 07 6D 71 D0 B3
07	7F 1F AD 12 21 6E BA A3 B4 DE 80 AE 2E E0 10 B7
08	CE 8A B0 38 A2 02 CA 11 63 3B A8 7A 83 64 30 26
09	7E 35 1E A6 E5 89 E2 D5 99 24 7C 19 68 03 F1 31
0A	90 3A D4 D6 F9 27 7B 2C BF 4E EA 74 5D 00 E4 9C
0B	29 4D 6F 6A F2 06 57 48 22 CC 70 92 4C D9 F4 D3
0C	E7 DC 61 3E EF 9F 8D E3 C0 D8 C9 D7 39 E9 0E 34
0D	46 53 E6 6C 55 B5 AB C4 B9 C5 8F DB A5 EB 50 1A
0E	4B 3D 04 86 76 B2 C8 36 88 13 A4 F5 2F 32 5B 62
0F	A1 F3 77 58 E1 E8 7D 67 9A FD 0C 65 C7 28 ED 51

Figure 11. Backward black-box4

	00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F
00	EA 31 BC 7C 64 06 79 CC B7 7F 3B 46 E4 18 16 60
01	DE D3 33 B2 6B 37 7A 1F 67 45 A7 0D C6 74 F3 5F
02	25 D0 B5 A3 92 2B F7 8A A8 48 7D 39 AE 71 D8 A1
03	CA 9C 28 17 19 38 53 21 8B 2F 73 8E 4D 07 61 A4
04	CD 97 E7 6D ECD 2 6A 22 AF C9 D1 01 DCA 2 9D 5C
05	DA 04 44 F9 02 EE B8 E5 D4 08 83 91 77 10 EF 20
06	A6 ED 50 56 C2 90 E6 E2 E2 69 42 4A 51 11 05 1D
07	F8 D6 D5 F1 8C C1 C0 CE F2 EB 35 6E 2C 8A 76 E8
08	47 4E DD B9 B1 AD C4 1E 52 1C 34 E0 A5 B6 1B FF
09	4F 26 14 E3 15 12 65 9F 7B 43 8F 80 B0 5D AA 96
0A	41 82 98 B4 5A C3 54 FC C7 CB 6C 49 7E 00 57 DB
0B	F7 24 C5 4C 68 BA 36 86 3C 9E 3F 2A B3 F6 8D 2D
0C	A0 CF 81 E1 84 59 0A 9B 89 BD AC 55 3A A9 94 58
0D	87 D7 BF 95 40 13 6F F5 88 E9 3D 63 4B 09 93 DF
0E	27 70 BB 75 FA 0E FD 5E F0 D9 0B 32 0F 5B 72 9A
0F	3E 99 29 C8 BE 23 1A 85 66 0C F4 62 03 30 AB FE

Figure 12. Backward black-box5

	00 01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 0A 0B 0C 0D 0E 0F
00	05 37 F2 D6 0A BF 14 6C B0 69 80 1A 79 E0 9B 83
01	5D 39 70 B7 F8 C7 44 87 A0 D0 86 FC 5C F5 0D E6
02	74 F0 D1 CD 35 B9 F1 CF 32 84 AE 47 CB 48 E9 9A
03	2E C2 45 BD B4 71 59 52 50 E7 A6 CC 43 E4 98 EF
04	A8 7B 21 B3 CA A3 67 DD 3A AA FA 01 DA 96 6F F4
05	0E 09 24 1C B6 D9 4D F9 CE B1 42 4E DE 63 91 3B
06	B2 3C 8A 0F 55 E5 29 8B 7A 6A 61 E8 4B F3 EC 64
07	93 95 A2 BA 4C B8 54 25 28 5E 81 56 53 16 65 5F
08	66 34 E3 75 C1 C9 DC D8 C5 3F 8F A1 72 60 EB 77
09	6D FE 90 10 85 92 17 46 1D FD 9E BB 7D 1F 5A A4
0A	5B 02 57 8D 94 03 19 DF 07 06 C6 04 12 00 D7 0C
0B	D4 41 83 99 78 3E AF 9F D5 AC EA BE EE 11 27 4A
0C	7E 15 C0 4F 68 2C F7 BC 73 1E 2D C8 20 B5 8C
0D	97 08 38 18 76 7F 9C DB 3D 23 22 F6 82 49 7C 31
0E	26 E2 40 E1 2A AD 58 AB FB 89 FF 62 51 30 8E D3
0F	6B C4 0B C3 A9 A7 9D 33 36 1B 2F 6E D5 A5 2B D2

Figure 13. Backward black-box6

2.3. Internal magic transposition

The Magic transposition acts as the second stage of the round transformation in the proposed algorithm. The main notation beyond the internal magic transposition is to map the values' positions to other different positions. The magic transposition stage also involves a cube of six dimensions whereby each dimension is arranged according to the doubly even magic square of 4*4 as shown in Figure 14. The magic square of doubly even order is a matrix of (4 m), whereby the order of matrix can be divided by 2 and 4 [24]. The core idea for the design magic cube primarily depends on a folded magic square notation that has presented in [25].

16	2	3	13	32	18	19	29	64	50	51	61	80	66	67	77	96	82	83	93	112	98	99	109
5	11	10	8	21	27	26	24	53	59	58	56	69	75	74	72	85	91	90	88	101	107	106	104
9	7	6	12	25	23	22	28	57	55	54	60	73	71	70	76	89	87	86	92	105	103	102	108
4	14	15	1	20	30	31	17	52	62	63	49	68	78	79	65	84	94	95	81	100	110	111	97

Figure 14. Six dimensions of doubly even magic square transposition

2.4. The internal linear matrices stages

The proposed cipher adopts six of new linear MDS codes with their inverses coefficients dedicated for each dimension cube as stated in (7-12). The linear stage is implemented with addition and multiplication operations. The essence mathematical clue is based on Galois field $GF(2^8)$ that works separately with each face in the cubic structure. The proposed linear codes can be represented as maximum distance separable (MDS) matrices. The linear MDS matrices code is implemented as a column-by-column multiplication modulo the reducible polynomial of x^4+1 .

$$\begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 04 & 07 & 04 & 06 \\ 06 & 04 & 07 & 04 \\ 04 & 06 & 04 & 07 \\ 07 & 04 & 06 & 04 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 04 & 06 & 04 & 07 \\ 07 & 04 & 06 & 04 \\ 04 & 07 & 04 & 06 \\ 06 & 04 & 07 & 04 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 05 & 07 & 05 & 06 \\ 06 & 05 & 07 & 05 \\ 05 & 06 & 05 & 07 \\ 07 & 05 & 06 & 05 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 05 & 06 & 05 & 07 \\ 07 & 05 & 06 & 05 \\ 05 & 07 & 05 & 06 \\ 06 & 05 & 07 & 05 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 07 & 05 & 06 & 05 \\ 05 & 07 & 05 & 06 \\ 06 & 05 & 07 & 05 \\ 05 & 06 & 05 & 07 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 07 & 05 & 06 & 05 \\ 05 & 07 & 05 & 06 \\ 06 & 05 & 07 & 05 \\ 05 & 06 & 05 & 07 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 04 & 05 & 06 & 06 \\ 06 & 04 & 05 & 06 \\ 06 & 06 & 04 & 05 \\ 05 & 06 & 06 & 04 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 0e & 0a & 0c & 09 \\ 09 & 0e & 0a & 0c \\ 0c & 09 & 0e & 0a \\ 0a & 0c & 09 & 0e \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 03 & 04 & 01 & 07 \\ 07 & 03 & 04 & 01 \\ 01 & 07 & 03 & 04 \\ 04 & 01 & 07 & 03 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 09 & 0b & 0b & 08 \\ 08 & 09 & 0b & 0b \\ 0b & 08 & 09 & 0b \\ 0b & 0b & 08 & 09 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 03 & 06 & 01 & 05 \\ 05 & 03 & 06 & 01 \\ 01 & 05 & 03 & 06 \\ 06 & 01 & 05 & 03 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{0,c} \\ S_{1,c} \\ S_{2,c} \\ S_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} 09 & 09 & 0b & 0a \\ 0a & 09 & 09 & 0b \\ 0b & 0a & 09 & 09 \\ 09 & 0b & 0a & 09 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S'_{0,c} \\ S'_{1,c} \\ S'_{2,c} \\ S'_{3,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The proposed MDS matrices size is 4*4 like the MDS of AES cipher which is responsible for achieving the confusion and diffusion scheme to the whole structure. The proposed matrices transformations have been chosen from the best solutions we have acquired. The search process for getting the proposed linear equations of order four was computerized automatically. The mathematical software was programmed with Visual Studio C# 2013 under the Windows-10 operating system of 64-bit CPU Intel (R) Core i7 2.65GHz and RAM 8-GB. The inverse MDS matrices linear codes are implemented by using the inverse matrix coefficients in backward operations. All the submitted MDS matrices have been verified as active equations by multiplying the forward matrices by backward matrices. The multiplication result gives the identity matrix for each couple of corresponding matrices. So, the decryption process in each round is implemented by multiplying the Inv-MDS code according to the dimension number with the corresponding encryption MDS code.

2.5. Key addition layer

This is the last stage in the round transformation and the most sensitive stage that determines the strength of the secret ciphering key. The key addition stage involves the key expansion technique for the key generation process that covers all the rounds. The ciphering sub-keys are generated by two complex functions for only one dimension can be shown in Figure 15. Each function consists of three complex operations that increase the complexity of the ciphering key and each one accepts 128-bit of initial entry key. The complex function includes three internal operations of subbyte operation, complement operation and XORed with the constant vector or byte-rotate process. The LSB byte in the ciphering key takes the mod operation for the number seven (mod 7) to determine which face or dimension in the cube through which the encryption process will be implemented in each round.

Figure 15. One dimension key generation algorithm of one-round

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Big data opened the door in front of several sophisticated challenges and numerous information security responsibilities. The proposed cipher can be analyzed from all directions to cover all design details and to figure out the internal operations. The cubic algorithm is designed with a solid round transformation that has six separate paths each of them traverses an independent algorithm. The selection path determines which cube dimension is selected and will be dedicated to encryption. The proposed algorithm adopts a strong secret key that makes the linear and differential attacks very hard. The proposed structure is a composed structure with multi-similar structures that work in parallel simultaneously. Moreover, each algorithm can work as an individual autonomous algorithm. The secret ciphering key is provided with two complex functions that work to prevent the weak/semi-weak sub-keys from appearance through the generation process. The round symmetry for the key scheduling adds an extra layer against the related-key attacks and the square attack. The proposed structure includes six active Black-box tables that apply a high nonlinearity and confusion against the linear and differential attacks. The magic shifting with six dimensions is a new direction for the design secrets with an optimal diffusion to defend the correlation attack. The six different linear MDS codes have been distributed into the proposed cubic dimensions independently. The product cipher with collected stages is affected greatly to the different propagation probabilities of the plaintext and ciphertext for the whole rounds. Furthermore, the product cipher will distribute the number of trails and weights for each bricklayer function iteratively. The differential properties for the algebraic aspects and the multiplicative inverse over Galois Field ($GF 2^8$) have been extended for multi-power.

The timing attack becomes impossible for the mathematical internal operations since the algorithm has a balance cubic structure. The balanced structure means that the same implementation time for the encryption and decryption operations in all dimensions. The multiplication process by the MDS code for the linear layer tends to be converged due to equality linear coefficients. The proposed MDS coefficients are almost convergent because they carry the same upper bound of coefficients. Thus, probably there is no leakage information throughout the computation process and consequently, the power analysis attack and timing attacks are very hard. The proposed cipher is focusing on increasing the security layer by preventing the attack from detecting the statistics' weakness. The ciphering sub-keys are implemented to enhance the security level by encountering all types of cryptanalysis attacks. The proposed cipher adopts an effective strategy for defeating the linear and differential attacks within a multi-dimensional framework. The whole randomness tests released by the National Institute and Standard Technology (NIST) have experimented on the acquired results. The outcome of these tests did not give any fluctuation at randomness boundaries. All of these aspects and tests are taken into account through the designing process. Simple tests for the speed measurement and a number of code lines of the proposed cipher and the original AES is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between the proposed model and the original AES

Algorithm cipher	Block cipher	Key length	No. of rounds	Clock cycle of key scheduling	Clock cycle of encryption process	Code size-assembly language
Cubic-dimension1	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	12050	13580	10430
Cubic-dimension2	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	12850	13595	10520
Cubic-dimension3	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	12670	13860	10380
Cubic-dimension4	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	12400	14670	10480
Cubic-dimension5	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	12890	14400	10600
Cubic-dimension6	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	12760	14870	10510
The standard AES	128-bit	128-bit	10-rounds	11050	12930	9150

The encryption and decryption implementation time is measured for the proposed cipher according to each dimension independently and compared with the AES standard cipher as shown in Figure 16. The implementation time of the decryption process for the proposed ciphers is varied smoothly from one- dimensional algorithm to another. The time differentiation is occurred due to the coefficients differences in the proposed mathematical equations.

Figure 16. Comparison of time implementation encryption/decryption process

4. CONCLUSION

A novel cubic symmetric cipher algorithm has been proposed and developed of round transformation with six dimensions and ten iterated rounds. The proposed cipher has the ability to encrypt the data with multi-dimensional algorithms that compensate for six collected cryptographic algorithms working together. The proposed algorithm includes various mathematical backgrounds of the finite field over $GF(2^8)$ and magic square mathematical formula. The developed cipher works to encrypt the 128-bit block of data for each dimension independently. Moreover, the main structure can be implemented in parallel from all directions of the cube to increase the speed of the encryption rate in busy servers. The cubic cipher provides a high margin of confidentiality and flexibility in the implementation. The implementation process can be individual or in parallel with a multi-dimensional structure to satisfy the big data needs and the development of technology in different disciplinary fields. The cubic cipher algorithm introduces a modern design structure with accepted results that are almost close to the results of the standard algorithms.

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